

DIETARY PATTERNS AND THEIR ASSOCIATION WITH BLOOD PRESSURE AMONG ADULT MALES IN DISTRICT SWAT

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Abstract

Background: Hypertension, obesity, and diabetes are major public health concerns in Pakistan. Dietary patterns play a critical role in the development of these conditions, yet limited evidence exists regarding their association with metabolic and socio-demographic factors in male adults of District Swat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Objectives: This study aimed to identify prevalent dietary patterns and examine their association with blood pressure, plasma glucose concentration, and socio-demographic characteristics among adult males.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted in male adults (n=400) of District Swat. Dietary intake was assessed using a 24-hour dietary recall and a food frequency questionnaire. Anthropometric measurements; weight, height, BMI and waist circumference were recorded following WHO recommendations. Principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to derive dietary patterns. Hypertension was defined as SBP \geq 140 mmHg and DBP \geq 90 mmHg. Fasting blood glucose was determined using a glucometer. Physical activity was measured using the Global Physical Activity Questionnaire. Statistical analyses were performed in SPSS using Chi-square tests, ANOVA, and multiple logistic regression.

Results: Most participants (34.5%) were aged 31–40 years; 52.8% were unmarried, and 42.8% had formal education. More than half (56.5%) reported no family history of chronic disease, and 54.5% were non-smokers. BMI classification revealed 9.8% obese, 40.9% overweight, and 40% normal-weight individuals. Overall, 59% were at risk of obesity and 44% at risk of hypertension. Dietary pattern 1 was associated with reduced risk of hypertension, while dietary pattern 2 increased the risk of diabetes without significant effects on central obesity or hypertension. High intake of dietary pattern 3 was linked to increased prevalence of hypertension (63%) in the third tertile.

Conclusion: Distinct dietary patterns were significantly associated with hypertension and diabetes risk among adult males in District Swat. Moderate intake of fats, carbohydrates, and proteins from all major food groups is recommended to reduce the burden of chronic diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Dietary patterns represent the combination of different foods and nutrients habitually consumed, along with their frequency. They provide a broader picture of nutrient intake and may therefore serve as a more prognostic indicator of disease risk than individual nutrients or supplements. Dietary pattern analysis is a comprehensive approach that assesses whether individuals consume a healthier mix of foods and explores its relationship with overall well-being (Parveen et al., 2016).

Globally, the prevalence of hypertension is approximately 26% among adults and is projected to rise to 29% within the next decade as populations age (Kearney et al., 2005). The risk of elevated blood pressure increases with age, and more than 50% of adults older than 60 years are likely to develop hypertension (Vasan et al., 2002). In Pakistan, hypertension is the most common non-communicable disease, affecting nearly 12 million people (Nishtar, 2003).

Dietary patterns are of particular importance in nutritional epidemiology, as they address the limitations of single-nutrient or single-food analyses. Conventional studies focusing on isolated nutrients often fail to capture the complex interactions among dietary components (Hoffmann et al., 2002). Variations in dietary patterns and lifestyles contribute to chronic diseases such as hypertension, stroke, diabetes mellitus, and cardiovascular diseases (CVD), which are major causes of premature mortality and disability worldwide. These conditions place additional burdens on already strained national health systems (WHO, 2003).

Both diabetes and hypertension are major risk factors for CVD and stroke, contributing substantially to healthcare costs and productivity losses. Consequently, dietary patterns have long been considered critical in epidemiological research on these diseases (Schulze & Hu, 2002). Hypertension, in particular, is a leading global public health challenge, affecting more than one billion people. Rapid economic development and urbanization have contributed to a nearly 33% increase in its prevalence, making it one of the

most common chronic diseases. Hypertension is multifactorial, influenced by dietary factors, alcohol consumption, high salt intake, and genetic predisposition (Zheng et al., 2016).

Over the past few decades, obesity has also risen dramatically worldwide, becoming a major risk factor for chronic diseases such as hypertension, CVD, and diabetes. Nutritional epidemiology has traditionally examined individual nutrient intake in relation to disease outcomes. However, because foods and nutrients are consumed together, their combined effects may differ from their isolated contributions (Satija et al., 2015). Cardiovascular diseases remain the leading cause of death globally (World Health Organization, 2005).

The prevalence of obesity and overweight among adolescents and young adults has become a serious public health concern in both developed and developing countries. Contributing factors include low physical activity, sedentary lifestyles, and increased consumption of energy-dense foods, sugary beverages, and fast foods (Borges et al., 2018).

Dietary patterns, being closer to modifiable behaviors than nutrient intakes, provide valuable insights for designing nutrition intervention programs (Hulshof et al., 2001). While the relationship between dietary patterns and chronic diseases has been extensively studied in developed countries, data remain limited for the Pakistani population. Therefore, the present study aims to identify the dietary patterns of young adults in District Swat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, and to examine their association with hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and central obesity.

Materials and Methods

Study Site & population

This study was conducted among adult males in District Swat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, using a cross-sectional study design. The district comprises two distinct regions—Upper and Lower Swat, representing a diverse population. From each region, four Tehsils were randomly selected. Within each Tehsil, four Union Councils were chosen, and each Union Council was further divided into four villages.

From each village, 100 participants were randomly recruited, yielding a total sample of 400 subjects. Eligible participants were middle-aged men aged ≥ 25 years.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All healthy male subjects aged ≥ 25 years were included. Individuals younger than 25 years or those with serious illnesses and were not willing to participate in the study were excluded.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was calculated based on the total population of the four selected villages in Swat, using Yamane's formula (1967):

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where,

N = Total population of randomly selected villages = 40712

e = Level of precision with 95% confidence level = 5% or 0.05

Putting the values:

$$\text{Sample size} = 40712 / 1 + 40712 (0.05)^2 = 399.8 \cong 400$$

Thus, the final sample size was 400 participants.

Dietary Intake Assessment

Dietary data were collected using a 24-hour dietary recall and a Food Frequency Questionnaire (FFQ). Interviews were conducted at participants' homes or other convenient locations.

Dietary Pattern Analysis

Dietary patterns were derived using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) applied to FFQ data. PCA identifies underlying dietary factors by grouping food items based on correlations. Factor loading matrices were computed for each food item across three dietary patterns. Foods with loadings ≥ 0.25 were considered strongly associated with a given pattern and were used to define and label the dietary patterns.

The suitability of factor analysis was confirmed using Bartlett's test of sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy. Both criteria were consistent with

established methodological standards (Schulze et al., 2013).

Anthropometric Measurements

Body weight was measured using a calibrated scale, with participants wearing light clothing and no shoes (Lean et al., 1995). Height was measured without shoes using a stadiometer. Waist circumference was recorded 1 cm above the navel at minimal respiration. Each measurement was taken twice following standardized protocols.

Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated as weight (kg) divided by height squared (m^2). Participants were categorized according to WHO guidelines (1995):

- Underweight: BMI < 18.5
- Normal weight: $18.5 \leq \text{BMI} < 24$
- Overweight: $24 \leq \text{BMI} < 28$
- Obese: BMI ≥ 28

Blood Pressure Measurement

Blood pressure was measured twice on the right arm by trained personnel, with participants seated and rested. A standard mercury sphygmomanometer with an appropriately sized cuff was used. The mean of the two readings was recorded. Hypertension was defined as systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg (Zhou, 2002).

Physical Activity Assessment

Physical activity was assessed using the Global Physical Activity Questionnaire (GPAQ). Activity levels were classified as low, moderate, or vigorous according to GPAQ analysis guidelines. Participants reported the frequency, duration, and intensity of their usual weekly activities during the preceding seven days.

Blood Glucose Measurement

Fasting blood glucose was measured using a portable glucometer. Participants with fasting glucose ≥ 110 mmol/L were classified as having elevated blood glucose, while those with values < 110 mmol/L were considered normal, following WHO criteria (Alberti et al., 1998).

Statistical Analysis

Data on socio-demographic characteristics, anthropometry, physical activity, dietary intake and patterns, blood glucose, and blood pressure were entered into SPSS (Version 20) for analysis. Associations between variables were examined using Chi-square tests, correlation analyses, and multiple logistic regression models.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic characteristics of subjects

Table-1 demonstrates socio-demographic attributes of the subjects. The mean age of the studied population was 39.4±12.17 years. 34.5% of the subjects were in the age of 31-40, 23.3% were in the age of 51-60, while 12.8% were in the age category of 41-50 years. Majority of the subjects were unmarried (52.8%) while 47.3% were married. 56 % were living in joint family system. Most of the subjects were graduated (42.8%) and a very few were illiterate (16%).

Table-1: Socio-demographic characteristics of subjects

Variables		Frequency (%) /Mean ± SD
Age (Years)		39.4±12.17
Age Categories	21-30	29.5 (29.5%)
	31-40	34.5 (34.5%)
	41-50	12.8 (12.8%)
	51-60	23.3 (23.3%)
Marital status	Single	52.8 (52.8%)
	Married	47.3 (47.3%)
	Student	24.0 (24.0%)
Occupation	Businessman	20.0 (20.0%)
	Farmers/Labors	17.9 (17.9%)
	Teacher	5.5 (5.5 %)
	Professional	19.0 (19.5%)
	Farmers	12.3 (12.3%)
Education	Illiterate	16.0 (16.0)
	Primary	10.5 (10.5)
	Matric	7.0 (7.0)
Family types	Bachelor	42.8 (42.8)
	Masters	23.8 (23.8)
	Joint	56 (56%)
	Nuclear	44 (44%)

%= percentage, SD= standard deviation

Anthropometric characteristics of subjects

Table-2 shows the anthropometric measurements of the subjects from the populace. The mean weight and height of the studied population were 74.35±9.42 kg and 169.263±4.11 cm respectively. The mean BMI was 25.95±3.02 kg/ m². Whereas 40% (n=16) individuals were found normal, 49.5% (n=198) were overweight and 9.8% (n=39) were obese. The mean waist circumference was 92.7±13.27 cm. Overall 41% (n=164) were in normal category and 59% (n=263) were at risk of central obesity according to WHO standards for the Asian population. The mean waist to

hip ratio was 0.951 where 76% (n=304) individuals were found normal as their waist to hip ratio was less than 1 and 23.3% (n=93) were overweight with greater than 1 waist to hip ratio.

It was observed in current study that majority of the study population have moderate physical activity and normally physical activity associated with onset of obesity and overweight. Iqbal et al. (2006) had reported in their study that only 28% of the highly educated population in Pakistan exercise on daily basis and found that 24% of the subjects had a BMI above then 30.

Table-2 Anthropometric characteristics of the subjects

Variables	Frequency (%) Means (SD)
Weight (kg)	74.35±9.42
Height	169.263±4.11
BMI Categories	Normal Overweight Obese
	163 (40.8%) 198 (49.5%) 39 (9.8%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.95±3.02
Waist circumference (cm)	92.71±13.27
	Normal At risk
	164 (41.0%) 236 (59.0%)
Hip circumference (cm)	96.38±10.33
Waist to hip ratio	0.951±0.087
WHR categories	Normal Overweight
	304 (76.0%) 93 (23.3%)

%= percentage, SD= standard deviation, WHR= waist to hip ratio, BMI= body mass index, cm= centimeter, kg= kilogram

Biological characteristics of the subjects

Table 3 shows the biological parameters of the study population. 92.8% (n=371) of the total subjects were found normal and 7.3% (n=29) were at risk of diabetes. 64.0% (n=264) had normal systolic blood pressure while 36.0% (n=144) had at risk of high systolic pressure. Diastolic blood pressure of the 73.8% (n=295) were found normal while 26.3% (n=105) were at risk. 44.0% (n=176) were at risk of hypertension.

In present study 59.0% people were at risk of obesity which may be a keen cause of development of hypertension. These results are supported by the findings of Anderson et al, 2001 who observed the relation of central obesity, high blood pressure and waist circumference. They further stated that hypertension increases with increment in age and that relation is independent of the gender.

Table-3 Biological characteristics of the subjects

Variables	Frequency (%) / Means± SD
Fasting Blood Glucose	94.57±15.96
FBS Categories	Normal At risk
	371(92.8%) 29 (7.3%)
Systolic Blood Pressure	137.59±14.01
	Normal At risk
	256 (64.0%) 144 (36%)
Diastolic Blood Pressure	86.72±6.712
	Normal At risk
	295 (73.8%) 105 (26.3%)
Hypertension	Normal At risk
	224 (56.0%) 176 (44.0%)

%= percentage, SD= standard deviation, FBS at risk ≥110, SBP at risk ≥ 90 mmHg, DBP ≥ 140 mmHg

Factors loading matrix for the major dietary patterns derived by PCA analysis

Table-4 shows three dietary patterns identified by Principal Components Analysis (PCA). The dietary patterns are Healthy pattern included (Fruit, fish, oil, whole grains), Sugar-Dairy rich pattern (fresh juices, honey, vegetables, yogurt and lassi) and unhealthy pattern (Carbonated drinks, rice, red meat, chicken, egg, samosa and pakorra).

Foods with factor loadings equal to or above 0.25 on a dietary pattern were considered to have a strong association with that pattern and

were considered most informative in labeling and describing the pattern. Previous researches proved that dietary pattern analysis can be useful in evaluating the multidimensional nature of diets. Mishra et al. (2002) reported different dietary patterns derived from FFQ by using factor analysis methodology. Similarly, Pakistani (Safdar et al., 2013) as well as South Asian (Satija et al., 2015) studies have demonstrated dietary pattern method as a useful tool for highlighting causal relation of diet and disease.

Table 4. Factors loading matrix for the major dietary patterns derived by PCA analysis.

Food Groups	COMPONENT		
	Healthy pattern	Sugar-Dairy richUnhealthy pattern	richUnhealthy pattern
Legumes	0.176	0.418	0.205
Fruit	0.317	0.299	0.114
Fresh Juices	-0.110	0.690	-0.072
Carbonated drinks	-.007	0.342	0.580
Grains	0.125	0.030	-0.025
Rice	0.229	-0.252	0.391
Red meat	-0.129	-0.009	0.680
Poultry Chicken	0.037	-0.090	0.535
Fish	0.270	0.010	0.091
Egg	-0.048	0.225	0.442
Samosa & Pakorra	0.132	0.373	0.439
Honey	0.212	0.647	-0.244
Oil	0.915	-0.032	0.037
C. Ghee	-0.858	0.120	0.221
C. vegetable	0.212	0.469	0.247
C.Milk	0.163	0.157	0.170
Yogurt and lassi	-0.157	0.453	0.121
Whole grains	0.255	0.094	0.237

Food items having factors loading more the 0.25 were highlighted, c= combine

Anthropometric and biological characteristics associated with adherence to Healthy Dietary pattern

Table 5(a) shows the mean values for anthropometric and biological characteristics across the tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern 1.

The mean weights were (74.07±0.783, 74.04±0.821, 74.94±0.846) and height (169.16±0.354, 169.16±0.353, 169.45±0.363) while the mean values of hip circumferences (97.15±0.572, 97.01±0.603, 98.14±0.626) and fasting blood sugar(s) were (95.52±1.455, 93.60±1.348, 94.55±1.340).

Table 5(a). Anthropometric and biological characteristics across the tertiles associated with adherence to Healthy Dietary pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern (Mean ± S.E)			P value
	1 (n=133)	2 (n=134)	3 (n=133)	
Weight	74.07±0.783	74.04±0.8211	74.94±0.846	0.677

Height	169.16±0.354	169.16±0.353	169.45±0.363	0.807
BMI	25.82±0.248	25.98±0.273	26.06±0.265	0.809
WC	93.12±0.903	93.92±0.875	93.76±0.994	0.811
HC	97.15±0.572	97.010±0.603	98.145±0.626	0.349
WTH	0.951±0.0070	0.955± 0.0076	0.948±0.0079	0.814
FBS	95.52±1.455	93.60±1.348	94.55±1.340	0.619
SYS	137.53±1.120	138.64±1.186	136.58±1.328	0.486
DIA	86.74±0.518	86.90±0.511	86.62±0.539	0.927

n=total number of subjects, HTN=Hypertension, WC= waist circumference, FBS= Fasting blood glucose, BMI= body mass index, WTH= waist to hip ratio, SYS= systolic, DIA= diastolic

Anthropometric and biological characteristics across the tertiles associated with adherence to Sugar-Dairy rich pattern

Table 5(b) shows the mean values for anthropometric and biological characteristics across the tertiles of Sugar-Dairy rich pattern. The mean weight was (74.22±0.890,

74.97±0.777, 73.94±0.779) and height (169.19±0.388, 169.48±0.333, 169.10±0.346) while the mean values of hip circumference (97.56±0.666, 97.70±0.590, 97.04±0.5426) and fasting blood sugar was (95.53±1.301, 94.52±1.223, 94.61±1.577).

Table5(b) Anthropometric and biological characteristics associated with adherence to Sugar-Dairy rich pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Sugar-Dairy rich pattern (Mean ± S.E)			p. values
	1 (n= 133)	2 (n= 134)	3 (n= 133)	
weight	74.22±0.890	74.97±0.777	73.85±0.779	0.618
Height	169.19±0.388	169.48±0.333	169.10±0.346	0.737
BMI	25.97±0.300	26.11±0.246	25.77±0.235	0.657
WC	93.43±1.022	94.40±0.854	92.97±0.889	0.535
HC	97.560±0.666	97.701±0.590	97.046±0.5429	0.721
WTH	0.946±0.0076	0.962±0.0063	0.945±0.0085	0.204
FBS	92.53±1.306	94.52±1.223	96.61±1.577	0.113
SYS	138.81±1.301	136.68±1.136	137.28±1.202	0.441
DIA	87.71±0.528	86.49±0.537	86.08±0.492	0.071

HTN=Hypertension, WC= waist circumference, FBS= Fasting blood glucose, BMI= body mass index, WTH= waist to hip ratio, SYS= systolic, DIA= diastolic

Anthropometric and biological characteristics across the tertiles associated with adherence to Unhealthy Dietary pattern

Table 5(c) shows the mean values for anthropometric and biological characteristics across the tertiles of Unhealthy dietary pattern. The mean weight was (73.91±0.83, 74.76±0.84, 74.37±0.84) and height (168.71±0.385, 169.11±0.32, 169.96±0.32) while the mean values of hip circumference (97.56±0.610, 97.70±0.623, 97.04±0.571) and fasting blood sugar was (94.35±1.508, 94.96±1.410, 94.36±1.214) across the tertiles.

Dietary patterns may be specific to a rural Pakistani population, they did not differ much

in the context of food items and food groups from dietary patterns derived in other population groups. Reddy et al. (2005) who reported that rural communities in South Asia have lower risk factors for hypertension and heart diseases than the urban populations. It may be due to the fact that the rural diets are largely based on whole grains, fresh vegetables and fruits combined with more physically work demanding occupations such as farming. Satija et al. (2015) have demonstrated dietary pattern method as a useful tool for highlighting causal relation of diet and disease. In present study mostly people were at risk of obesity in all three dietary patterns which may be a keen cause of

development of hypertension. These results are supported by the findings of Anderson et al. (2001) who observed the relation of central obesity, high blood pressure and waist

circumference. They further stated that hypertension increases with increasing age and that relation is independent of the gender.

Table5(c). Anthropometric and biological characteristics across the tertiles associated with adherence to Unhealthy Dietary pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Unhealthy Dietary pattern (Mean± S.E)			P. Value
	1 (n=133)	2 (n=134)	3 (n=133)	
Weight	73.91±0.830	74.76±0.842	74.37±0.779	0.764
Height	168.71±0.385	169.11±0.345	169.96±0.328	0.041
BMI	26.06±0.257	26.12±0.268	25.68±0.260	0.0437
WC	93.37±0.981	93.82±0.916	93.61±0.876	0.942
HC	97.52±0.610	97.19±0.623	97.59±0.571	0.879
WHR	0.951±0.0078	0.956±0.0067	0.945±0.00810	0.584
FBS	94.35±1.508	94.96±1.410	94.36±1.214	0.939
SYS	137.63±1.165	138.20±1.241	136.92±1.240	0.758
DIA	86.26±0.521	86.97±0.511	87.04±0.534	0.503

HTN=Hypertension, WC= waist circumference, FBS= Fasting blood glucose, BMI= body mass index, WTH= waist to hip ratio, SYS= systolic, DIA= diastolic

Percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics across tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern

Table 6(a) demonstrate the percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics, which shows mostly subjects were in age of 30-40

which are 33.1%, 35.1% and 35.3% across the tertiles. 54.9% were single in tertile 3. 17.2% were illiterate and 51.5% were graduates in tertile 2. 66.2% had moderate activity in tertile 3.

Table 6(a). Percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics across tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern			P value	
	1 (n=133)	2 (n=134)	3 (n=133)		
Age categories	20-30	45(33.8%)	33(24.6%)	40(30.1%)	0.707
	31-40	44(33.1%)	47(35.1%)	47(35.3%)	
	41-50	17(12.8%)	17(12.7%)	17(12.8%)	
	51-60	27(20.3%)	37(27.6%)	29(21.8%)	
Marital status	Married	64(48.9%)	64(47.8%)	60(45.1%)	0.819
	Single	68(51.1%)	70(52.2%)	73(54.9%)	
Education Categories	Illiterate	21(15.8%)	23(17.2%)	20(15.0%)	0.221
	Primary	13(9.8%)	13(9.7%)	16(12.0%)	
	Matriculation	13(9.8%)	6(4.5%)	9(6.8%)	
	Graduation	51(38.3%)	69(51.5%)	51(38.3%)	
Smoking	Higher	35(26.3%)	23(17.2%)	37(27.8%)	0.796
	Smokers	36(27.1%)	37(27.6%)	44(33.1%)	
	Non smokers	76(57.1%)	75(56.0%)	67(50.4%)	
Physical Activity	Vigorous	30(22.6%)	26(19.4%)	27(20.3%)	0.972
	Moderate	85(63.9%)	88(65.7%)	88(66.2%)	
	Sedentary	18(13.5%)	20(14.9%)	18(13.5%)	

%= percentage

Percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics across the tertiles of Sugar-Dairy rich pattern

Table 6(b) shows the percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics across tertiles in Sugar-Dairy rich pattern. 36.8% were in the age of 30-40 in tertile 3. Marital status of the

subjects in dietary pattern 2 shows 60.9% were single as shown in tertile 1. Education categories show the percent distribution for graduated subjects which are 47.4%, 40.3% and 30.8 across the tertiles. And majority of the subjects had moderate physical activity.

Table 6(b). Percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics across the tertiles of Sugar-Dairy rich pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Sugar-Dairy rich pattern			p-values	
	1 (n=133)	2 (n=134)	3 (n=133)		
Age categories	20-30	43 (32.3%)	42 (31.3%)	33(24.8%)	0.385
	31-40	46 (34.6%)	43 (32.1%)	49(36.8%)	
	41-50	11 (8.3%)	22(16.4%)	18(13.5%)	
	51-60	33 (24.8%)	27(20.1%)	33(24.8%)	
Marital Status	Married	52(39.1%)	71(53.0%)	66(49.6%)	0.060
	Single	81(60.9%)	63(47.0%)	67(50.4%)	
Education Categories	Illiterate	19(14.3%)	17(12.7%)	28(21.1%)	0.228
	Primary	12(9.0%)	14(10.4%)	16(12.0%)	
	Matriculation	11(8.3%)	13(9.7%)	4(3.0%)	
	Graduation	63(47.4%)	54(40.3%)	54(40.6%)	
Smoking	Higher	28(21.1%)	36(26.9%)	31(23.3%)	0.294
	Smokers	36(27.1%)	40(29.9%)	41(30.8%)	
	Non smokers	81(60.9%)	72(53.7%)	65(48.9%)	
Physical Activity	Ex-smoker	16(12.0%)	22(16.4%)	27(20.3%)	0.256
	Vigorous	22(16.5%)	29(21.6%)	32(24.1%)	
	Moderate	86(64.7%)	90(67.2%)	85(63.9%)	
	Sedentary	25(18.8%)	15(11.2%)	16(12.0%)	

%= percentage

Percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics across tertiles of Unhealthy Dietary pattern

Table 6(c) shows the percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics for Unhealthy Dietary pattern. There are four age categories the high distribution is for category 30-40 which are 36.8%, 31.3% and 35.3%. In this pattern majority of the subjects were non-smoker their percent distribution is 60.2%, 53.0% and 50.45 across the tertile 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

In our study socio-demographic characteristics and physical activity have major influence with dietary patterns. Several studies described the role of socio demographic factors and dietary patterns. Sodjinou et al. (2009) concluded in

their study that early life environment like education, socioeconomic status, family meal frequency and home availability of healthy food were positively associated with the food patterns which may cause several health problems. Majority of the subjects in our study population have moderate physical activity. Iqbal et al. (2006) had reported in their study that only 28% of the highly educated population in Pakistan exercise on daily basis and found that 24% of the subjects had a BMI above then 30. Some researchers have suggested that smoking had serious outcomes in the onset of chronic diseases and hypertension (Shahab et al, 2010). Population studies show that social factors can also influence diet patterns (Olinto et al, 2011).

Table 6(c). Percent distribution of socio demographic characteristics across tertiles of Unhealthy Dietary pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Unhealthy Dietary pattern			p-values
	1 (n=133)	2 (n=134)	3 (n=133)	
Age categories				
20-30	40(30.1%)	42(31.3%)	36(27.1%)	0.786
31-40	49(36.8%)	42(31.3%)	47(35.3%)	
41-50	13(9.8%)	17(12.7%)	21(15.8%)	
51-60	31(23.3%)	33(24.6%)	29(21.8%)	
Marital status				
Married	68(51.1%)	59(44.0%)	32(46.6%)	0.501
Single	65(48.9%)	75(50.0%)	71(53.4%)	
Education categories				
Illiterate	18(13.5%)	26(19.4%)	20(15.0%)	0.213
Primary	21(15.8%)	10(7.5%)	11(8.3%)	
Matriculation	8(6.0%)	12(9.0%)	8(6.0%)	
Graduation	59(44.1%)	57(42.5%)	55(41.4%)	
Higher	27(20.3%)	29(21.6%)	39(29.3%)	
Smoking				
Smokers	34(25.6%)	37(27.6%)	46(34.6%)	0.338
Non smokers	80(60.2%)	71(53.0%)	67(50.4%)	
Ex-smoker	19(14.3%)	26(19.4%)	20(15.0%)	
Physical Activity				
Vigorous	26(19.5%)	34(25.4%)	23(17.3%)	0.00
Moderate	89(66.9%)	80(59.7%)	92(69.2%)	
Sedentary	18(13.5%)	20(14.9%)	18(13.5%)	

%= percentagePercent distribution of physiological and biological characteristics across the tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern

Table 7(a) demonstrates the percent obesity increases across the tertiles of this distribution across the tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern (57.1%, 59.7%, and 60.2%). No significant effect was established for fasting hypertension declines with increase in dietary intake of this pattern while the risk of central blood sugar.

Table 7(a). Percent distribution of physiological and biological characteristics across the tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Healthy Dietary pattern			χ^2	p-value	
	1 (n=133)	2 (n=134)	3 (n=133)			
HTN	Normal	n 72	74	81	1.432	0.489
		% 31.7%	32.6%	35.7%		
	At risk	n 61	60	52		
		% 35.3%	34.7%	30.1%		
Systolic	Normal	n 83	86	87	0.264	0.876
		% 62.4%	64.2%	65.4%		
	At risk	n 50	48	46		
		% 37.6%	35.8%	34.6%		
Diastolic	Normal	n 98	98	99	0.059	0.971
		% 73.7%	73.1%	74.4%		
	At risk	n 35	36	34		
		% 26.3%	26.9%	25.6%		
WC	Normal	n 57	54	53	0.290	0.865
		% 42.9%	40.3%	39.8%		
	At risk	n 76	80	80		
		% 57.1%	59.7%	60.2%		

FBS	Normal	n	124	124	124	0.066	0.967
		%	93.2%	92.5%	93.2%		
	At risk	n	9	10	9		
		%	6.8%	7.5%	6.8%		

HTN=Hypertension, WC= waist circumference, FBS= Fasting blood glucose, %= percentage

Percent distribution of physiological and biological characteristics across the tertiles of Sugar-dairy rich pattern

In this pattern hypertension shows no significant effect across the tertiles while the

risk of fasting blood glucose increases across the tertiles (5.3%, 6.0% and 9.8%). The waist circumference has also irregular risk across the tertiles in this dietary pattern which are 54.1% in first tertile and 60.9% in third tertile.

Table 7(b). Percent distribution of physiological and biological characteristics across the tertiles of Sugar-Dairy rich pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Sugar-Dairy rich pattern					χ^2	p-values
			1 (n=133)	2 (n=134)	3 (n=133)		
HTN	Normal	n	75	71	81	1.715	0.424
		%	56.4%	53.0%	60.9%		
	At risk	n	58	63	52		
		%	43.6%	47.0%	39.1%		
Systolic	Normal	n	86	84	86	0.15	0.927
		%	64.7%	62.7%	64.7%		
	At risk	n	47	50	47		
		%	35.3%	37.3%	35.3%		
Diastolic	Normal	n	88	99	108	7.769	0.021
		%	66.2%	73.9%	81.2%		
	At risk	n	45	35	25		
		%	33.8%	26.1%	18.8%		
WC	Normal	n	61	51	52	1.979	0.372
		%	45.9%	38.1%	39.1%		
	At risk	n	72	83	81		
		%	54.1%	61.9%	60.9%		
FBS	Normal	n	126	126	120	2.407	0.300
		%	94.7%	94.7%	94.7%		
	At risk	n	7	8	13		
		%	5.3%	6.0%	9.8%		

HTN=Hypertension, WC= waist circumference, FBS= Fasting blood glucose %= percentage, χ^2 =chi-square

Percent distribution of physiological and biological characteristics across the tertiles of unhealthy dietary pattern

Table 7(c) shows percent distribution across the tertiles of this pattern. The risk of hypertension increases as dietary intake from this pattern increases such as 39.1% in first tertile, 43.3% in second tertile and 47.4% in third tertile respectively. Waist circumference had no significant effect with this dietary pattern while fasting blood sugar decreases as dietary intake from this pattern increases (9.8% in first tertile,

6.7% in second tertile and 4.5% in third tertile respectively).

Risk of hypertension declines with increase in dietary intake of healthy dietary pattern including fruits, fish, oil and whole grains while central obesity increases across the tertiles of same dietary pattern. Such results are also found by Reddy et al. (2005) who reported that rural communities in South Asia have lower risk factors for hypertension and heart diseases than the urban populations. It may be due to the fact that the rural diets are largely based on

whole grains, fresh vegetables and fruits combined with more physically work demanding occupations such as farming. Alonso et al. (2004) and Bazzano et al. (2003) also mentioned in their findings that a considerable amount of evidence from epidemiological studies and randomized control trials has shown an inverse relationship between fresh fruit and vegetable intake and Hypertension. These characteristics of fruit and vegetables are still undecided but may be related to its nutrient contents which are highly

rich in potassium, magnesium with very low amount of sodium.

The highest tertile of sugar-dairy rich pattern showed the increased level of blood glucose, characterized by dairy products like lassi, yogurt and honey may cause the increased in blood glucose level. Same results were also found by van Dam et al. (2002) who reported that western dietary pattern included dairy products and sweets were associated with risk of type2 diabetes.

Table. 7(c). Percent distribution of physiological and biological characteristics across the tertiles of unhealthy dietary pattern

Variables	Tertiles of Unhealthy Dietary pattern			χ^2 1.853	p-values 0.396		
	1 (n=133)	2 (n=134)	3 (n=133)				
HTN	Normal	n	81	76	70	1.634	0.442
		%	60.9%	56.7%	52.6%		
	At risk	n	52	58	63		
		%	39.1%	43.3%	47.4%		
Systolic	Normal	n	90	86	80	2.430	0.297
		%	67.7%	64.2%	60.2%		
	At risk	n	43	48	53		
		%	32.3%	35.8%	39.8%		
Diastolic	Normal	n	103	100	92	1.436	0.488
		%	77.4%	74.6%	69.2%		
	At risk	n	30	34	41		
		%	22.6%	25.4%	30.8%		
WC	Total	n	133	134	133	2.855	0.240
		%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
	Normal	n	54	60	50		
		%	40.6%	44.8%	37.6%		
FBS	At risk	n	79	74	83	9.8%	6.7%
		%	59.4%	55.2%	62.4%		
	Normal	n	120	125	127		
		%	90.2%	93.3%	95.5%		
At risk	n	13	9	6	9.8%	6.7%	
	%	9.8%	6.7%	4.5%			

HTN=Hypertension, WC= waist circumference, FBS= Fasting blood glucose, %= percentage

Crude and adjusted odds ratios (95% confidence intervals) for hypertension across the tertiles of dietary patterns

Table 8 (a) shows association and risk of hypertension across the tertiles of three dietary patterns of the present study. The findings clearly demonstrated that the risk of hypertension decreases across the tertiles of healthy dietary pattern which included fruit, fish and whole grains items [(adjusted Odds

Ratios & 95% CI: 0.713(0.385-1.320) in second tertile vs 0.681(0.369-1.258) in third tertile]. While unhealthy dietary pattern shows increased risk in the highest tertile (adjusted Odds Ratios & 95%CI: 1.652(0.884-3.089).

In the current study people who were following healthy dietary pattern categorized by fruit, fish, oil, and whole grain had lower risk of hypertension. But these outcomes became non-significant after adjusting for subjects age,

gender, and other life factors. There may be a few explanations behind this perception in our data. Initially, dietary patterns might not impact the predominance of hypertension in our population in contrast with other risk factors, for example, socioeconomic and anthropometric factors. Furthermore, a few analysts recommend that the Asian cooking technique which includes stir frying, use of saturated fat and over-cooking of vegetables may partially clarify the null or no affiliation seen among Asians for diets rich in fruit and vegetables. Such results are also found by Reddy et al. (2005) who reported that rural communities in South Asia have lower risk factors for hypertension and heart diseases than

the urban populations. It may be due to the fact that the rural diets are largely based on whole grains, fresh vegetables and fruits combined with more physically work demanding occupations such as farming. Alonso et al. (2004) and Bazzano et al. (2003) also mentioned in their findings that a considerable amount of evidence from epidemiological studies and randomized control trials has shown an inverse relationship between fresh fruit and vegetable intake and Hypertension. These characteristics of fruit and vegetables are still undecided but may be related to its nutrient contents which are highly rich in potassium, magnesium with very low amount of sodium.

Table. 8(a). Crude and adjusted odds ratios (95% confidence intervals) for hypertension across the tertiles of different dietary patterns.

HYPERTENSION CRUDE ODD RATIOS			
Tertiles	Healthy dietary pattern	Sugar-Dairy rich pattern	Unhealthy dietary pattern
	Odds ratio (95% CI)	Odds ratio (95%CI)	Odds ratio (95%)
1	Reference	Reference	Reference
2	0.954 (0.586-1.551)	1.220 (0.688-1.824)	1.209 (0.735-1.987)
3	0.755 (0.0462-1.234)	0.780 (0.473-1.286)	1.451 (0.883-2.385)
HYPERTENSION ADJUSTED ODD RATIOS			
Tertiles	Healthy dietary pattern	Sugar-Dairy rich pattern	Unhealthy dietary pattern
	Odds ratio (95% CI)	Odds ratio (95%CI)	Odds ratio (95%)
1	Reference	Reference	Reference
2	0.713 (0.385-1.320)	1.343 (0.727-2.481)	1.271 (0.680-2.374)
3	0.681 (0.369-1.258)	0.867 (0.455-1.652)	1.652 (0.884-3.089)

Adjusted for age, marital status, education, smoking status and physical activity, %= percentage, DP= dietary pattern, CI= class interval

Odds ratios (95% confidence intervals) for Fasting blood glucose across the tertiles of Dietary patterns.

Table 8(b) shows the crude and adjusted odd ratios for fasting blood glucose which demonstrate that the risk decreases significantly in adjusted models across the tertiles of Dietary pattern 3 (AOR: 0.275, 95% CI (0.082-0.926; p=0.037) while the risk increases with dietary pattern 2 as evident by the higher adjusted odds

in the highest tertile (AOR: 1.859, 95 % CI (0.586-5.896).

Fasting blood glucose level had non-significant inverse relation with unhealthy dietary pattern contrary to other studies in the literature like Schulze and Hu (2002) reported in their study that higher intake of junk foods, fat meat, cakes and chocolates were positively associated with the risk of being hyperglycaemic in men but less strongly in women. It may be due to the fact that our FFQ has limited food items due to

which we were unable to capture the amount and type of individual food items consumed. However, there are studies which shows inconsistent results or they fail to establish any relation of health food items with the biomarkers of non-communicable diseases (Hajjar *et al.*, 2006).

In the current study risk of higher blood glucose level was observed with higher intake of sugar-dairy rich pattern as evident by the adjusted odds in the highest tertile (AOR: 1.859, 95 % CI (0.586-5.896). This pattern is heavily enriched with energy dense food items

such as honey, sweet and deserts, refined grains and high fat dairy products. Similarly, Van Dam *et al.* (2002) conducted a follow up study in male adult's population of United States. During 12 years of follow-up, they documented 1321 cases of type 2 diabetes. And reported that western dietary pattern (characterized by high-fat dairy products, refined grains, and sweets and desserts) was associated with an increased risk for type 2 diabetes (relative risk, 1.59 [CI, 1.32 to 1.93].

Table 8(b). Odds ratios (95% confidence intervals) for Fasting blood glucose across the tertiles of Dietary patterns.

CRUDE FASTING BLOOD SUGAR			
Tertiles	Healthy dietary pattern	Sugar-Dairy rich pattern	Unhealthy dietary pattern
	Odds ratio (95% CI)	Odds ratio (95%CI)	Odds ratio (95%)
1	Reference	Reference	Reference
2	1.125 (0.438-2.892)	1.271 (0.442-3.655)	0.581 (0.235-1.438)
3	0.961 (0.365-2.529)	2.347 (0.881-6.255)	0.370 (0.133-1.030)
ADJUSTED ODD RATIOS FASTING BLOOD GLUCOSE			
Tertiles	Healthy dietary pattern	Sugar-Dairy rich pattern	Unhealthy dietary pattern
	Odds ratio (95% CI)	Odds ratio (95%CI)	Odds ratio (95%)
1	Reference	Reference	Reference
2	0.937 (0.313-2.811)	1.136 (0.336-3.842)	0.391 (0.133-1.153)
3	0.989 (0.324-3.022)	1.859 (0.586-5.896)	0.275 (0.082-0.926)

*Adjusted for age, marital status, education, smoking status and physical activity
DP= dietary pattern, CI= class interval

Crude and adjusted odds ratios (95% confidence intervals) for waist circumference across the tertiles of Dietary patterns.

Table 8(c) shows crude and adjusted odd ratios for the risk of obesity with 95% confidence interval in all three dietary patterns. Subjects of third tertile of Dietary pattern 3 had higher odds for obesity (Adjusted OR: 1.296, 95% CI (0.728-2.307).

Peoples consuming unhealthy dietary pattern having food items like carbonated drinks, rice, samosa and pakorra were at high risk of obesity

but not significantly associated. It may be because of physical activity. An interesting observation that was seen in our data set and that may possibly support our findings for the unhealthy dietary pattern and central obesity was the fact that less physically active subjects were found in the highest tertile of dietary pattern 3. Normally physical activity and weight control may reduce the risk of central obesity. However, this should be further investigated. It was observed in current study that majority of the study population have moderate physical

activity. Iqbal et al. (2006) had mentioned in their study that only 28% of the highly educated population in Pakistan exercise on

daily basis and found that 24% of the subjects had a BMI above then 30.

Table 8(c). Crude and adjusted odds ratios (95% confidence intervals) for waist circumference across the tertiles of Dietary patterns.

CRUDE WAIST CIRCUMFERENCE ODD RATIOS			
Tertiles	Healthy dietary pattern	Sugar-Dairy rich pattern	Unhealthy dietary pattern
	Odds ratio (95% CI)	Odds ratio (95%CI)	Odds ratio (95%)
1	Reference	Reference	Reference
2	1.089 (0.667-1.779)	1.390 (0.850-2.275)	0.809 (0.493-1.326)
3	1.102 (0.674-2.1.801)	1.333 (0.811-2.192)	1.077 (0.652-1.779)
ADJUSTED WAIST CIRCUMFERENCE ODD RATIOS			
Tertiles	Healthy dietary pattern	Sugar-Dairy rich pattern	Unhealthy dietary pattern
	Odds ratio (95% CI)	Odds ratio (95%CI)	Odds ratio (95%)
1	Reference	Reference	Reference
2	0.807 (0.456-1.428)	0.722 (0.405-1.288)	0.829 (0.468-1.468)
3	1.094 (0.620-1.932)	1.191 (0.676-2.101)	1.296 (0.728-2.307)

Adjusted for age, marital status, education, smoking status and physical activity
 DP= dietary pattern, CI= class interval, WC= waist circumference

Conclusion

The outcomes provide baseline information about the dietary patterns and their relation with some chronic diseases like hypertension, diabetes and central obesity and socio demographic characteristics in the male adult’s population of District Swat. The results concluded that the risk of hypertension may decrease among the male adult population of Swat by following healthy dietary pattern including fruit, fish, whole grain and oil while the risk increases with unhealthy dietary pattern categorized by carbonated drinks, rice, red meat, chicken, samosa and pakora. Further, an increment in fasting blood glucose level and obesity was evidenced by sugar-dairy rich dietary pattern.

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